

HERE'S ANOTHER WAY (OR 3)

HYPNOSIS IS
BECOMING A
DEFAULT
ENGAGEMENT
STRATEGY.

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THE CONTEXT

AND

A SENSORY HISTORY MANIFESTO (2021)

ENVIRONMENT

IN WHICH WE

SENSE HAS

BEEEN

PROFOUNDLY

ALTERED.

EVEN THE VIOLENCE DONE TO THE SENSES BY WARS, HURRICANES, TORNADOES, AND EARTHQUAKES IS MODEST IN SCALE AND SCOPE COMPARED TO THIS SENSOR REVOLUTION.

MARK M. SMITH

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Attention is the delicate difference between the bot-driven hype behind your accounts and genuine human engagement with your online Self. Attention is a precious, and increasingly endangered resource. Attention is also a precious and uniquely *human* resource.

Inattention isn't new. But the amount of content available for consumption is absolutely unprecedented. We don't have enough thumbs nor hours in the day to scroll through the endless amounts of media made possible by streaming, AI, and automation.

As a member of the digital multiverse, you too, can game clicks, views, and even conversion by hacking attention.

IF YOU ARE STILL IN
THE BUSINESS OF
MAINTAINING A
DIGITAL PRESENCE,
THERE'S A
CRITICALLY
ENDANGERED
RESOURCE WE
MUST DISCUSS:

**THE PEOPLE'S
ATTENTION**

Attention

Gimmicks and rage-bait are timeless, seductive, and effective tools to this end. They play to the amygdala, the limbic system—the actual emergency alert system of the human body— zombie-fying us in the process.

We tend to (mindlessly) scroll more slowly, (mindlessly) watch longer, (mindlessly) click faster, and (mindlessly) react intensely to the content that is most likely to elicit a strong reaction—all behaviors a well-trained bot could mimic just as easily— **thus turning mindlessness into a habit of consumption.**

Building an editorial or content strategy (for humans) with actual strategy (for humans), however, is the key to deep, meaningful engagement. In fact, when done well, it may even build trust with your audience.

So—if you care—design with care. Design with empathetic rigor. And design with intention.

**HERE ARE A FEW
WAYS HOW.**

BREAK THE
BREAK THE
SUS
PROLL
PRES
PONS
BY

**HOW DO YOU HAVE
FUN WITH FIRST-TIME
GUESTS AND
VISITORS TO YOUR
WINDOW OF THE
DIGITAL MULTIVERSE?**

**INVITE
DELIGHT**

THIS CONTENT IS AN INVITATION TO DELIGHT. IT'S A WELCOME DISTRACTION IN YOUR AUDIENCE'S DAY. THEY'RE INVITED TO STEP OUT OF REALITY FOR A MOMENT TO SAMPLE A BIT OF JOY AND HAVE FUN WITH YOU.

laugh first · memes matter · have fun · play a game · pretend we're at a bar,
a bus stop, or water cooler · beautify the feed · spark awe & wonder

**LITERALLY: FEATURE
HUMANS. THIS CONTENT IS
ALL ABOUT DEPUTIZING
THE AUDIENCE AS A
COMMUNITY OF CARE
INSTEAD OF MERE
SPECTATORS.**

FEATURE HUMANS

HUMANS COMPEL US TO ACT HUMANELY; MORE LIKE CO-CONSPIRATORS AND NEIGHBORS RATHER THAN HOSTILE WITNESSES OR A JURY AT TRIAL. IT'S ABOUT CREATING SPACE FOR YOUR COMMUNITY TO SHED THE COMPULSION TO PERFORM FOR SECONDHAND ENGAGEMENT METRICS ON YOUR PAGES, PLATFORMS, CHANNELS AND SERVERS. EXPLICITLY INVITE YOUR AUDIENCE TO SUSPEND JUDGMENT BY MODELING HUMAN BEING AND HUMAN REACTION IN YOUR CONTENT.

prompt the chat accordingly (WWYD?) · hide likes · poll instead of comment · invite folks to add to the content rather than react only

INVITE YOUR AUDIENCE TO
ZONE OUT. GET BORED.
ENCOURAGE YOUR
AUDIENCE TO DAYDREAM
INSTEAD OF LIKING AND
SHARING AND
COMMENTING.

BREATHE OUT

IT'S EASY TO FEEL OVERWHELMED BY THE MAGNITUDE, THE INTENSITY, AND THE MONOTONY OF THE ALGORITHM. EVERY 'LIKE', COMMENT, OR HESITANT GLANCE YIELDS MORE OF THE SAME. MAKE ROOM FOR YOUR DIGITAL AUDIENCE TO BREATHE. DO IT VISUALLY. DO IT TONALLY. OR MAYBE DO IT BY MODELING HOW TO *DO NOTHING* ON SCREEN. HELP YOUR AUDIENCE BREAK THE SCROLL BY HELPING THEM TUNE IN TO THEIR OWN PHYSICAL BODIES AND PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENTS.

invite nature and wildlife to the feed · invite your guests to, *literally*, exhale · slow down the pace of narration, music, shot changes

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